

A Cultural Study On Opera Changzheng

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 26, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: March 27, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Chinese Epic Opera, The Long March, Musical Analysis, Artistic Image, Shaping, Research</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7775342</p>	<p><i>Opera, a jewel in the world's art treasury, is the most artistic art genre. The art form of opera originated in Italy and has been introduced to China for more than 100 years. The art of opera has taken root in China and combined with the Chinese musical style to form a genre of folk opera with unique Chinese characteristics, which has given Chinese folk opera a place in the world of opera. Since entering the twenty-first century, China has experienced unprecedented and rapid development in all fields. In the field of culture and the arts, too, there has been vigorous and rapid development, and the opera business has once again entered a period of prosperity. This paper selects the newly composed large-scale epic opera "The Long March", which is representative of the new era, as the object of study, and conducts a comprehensive research on the creation background, musical analysis, singing style and stage performance of the main characters, as well as the influence of the opera "The Long March" on the creation of Chinese opera in the new era. The main part is divided into seven chapters.</i></p>

Introduction

After thinking deeply and finally deciding on the research direction, the author began to collect and sort out the relevant literature. Based on the established research direction, I have collected almost all academic papers, monographs, journals and magazines related to this topic, and even video materials related to operas, movies and TV series. Among the existing literature reviewed and referred to, the author has made a detailed summary and generalization, and organized the related materials that are more closely related, and elaborated them according to different categories, such as doctoral and master's theses, journals and magazines, and monographs. Among them, there are 12 doctoral and master's theses, 8 journals and magazines, and 2 monographs.

Doctoral and Master's Theses

On the germination and development of opera in China, Dr. Mannovo in his dissertation "The Birth of Chinese Opera" gives a detailed account of the various periods of the gestation, development and even maturation of Chinese opera in the early part of the last century. In particular, he provides a clear analysis and elaboration of the many issues that arose during the budding period of opera exploration in China. He also offers his own insights into the long-standing academic debate over "what is Chinese opera" and "what is the way out". These arguments give the author a clearer understanding of the concepts related to this topic.

Dr. Zhang Qiang, in his article "A Study on the Performing Arts of Folk Opera in the Early Period of New China (1949-1966)", describes in detail the development of Chinese folk opera from its birth to its gradual formation of its own style only after the founding of New China, as well as its ability to follow the localized style during the difficult period of the war, and its ability to continuously draw on the essence of opera performance, as well as the creative techniques of Western opera. and eventually formed his own artistic characteristics. He summarized the characteristics of the opera: the singing style is mainly national, the lyricism and documentary are fused, and the singing and acting are balanced with each other. Based on the difficult path of exploration of Chinese folk opera, he also summarizes many issues worth exploring and also provides valuable experiences. All these ideas are very informative for the writing of this thesis.

In his article "Research on the Performing Arts of Chinese National Opera since the New Era (1976-2016)," Dr. Li Zixian elaborates on the overview of the development of opera in China since the new era. He explains in detail from the emancipation of ideas during the period of artistic recovery, to the borrowing and integration of Western ideas as they gradually entered, to the innovation and development made in the context of China's reality. He also presents case studies of several accomplished contemporary artists in the field of opera performance, as well as exploring and reflecting on theories of Chinese folk opera performance since the new era. He stands at a certain height to analyze the current situation and prospects of the art of folk opera performance, and also offers his personal insights. His insightful analyses have inspired the author.

In his article "A Study on the Artistic Style of Singing in Chinese Folk Opera," Dr. Yang Quanhai outlines the overview of the development of Chinese folk opera. He elaborates on three aspects of folk opera, namely, its cultural characteristics, aesthetic staging, and the establishment of performance system. He firstly discusses the

singing style of Chinese folk opera under the perspective of aesthetic dimension, from national aesthetics and diversified aesthetics, period aesthetics and classical aesthetics, all of which are explained in more detail; secondly, he analyzes the singing style of Chinese folk opera under the perspective of performance theory, from the juxtaposition of nationalization and Western Europeanization, the complementarity of diversification and homogenization, the conflict between internationalization and localization, and the inheritance of traditionalization and periodization. The study of Chinese folk opera is particularly innovative and enlightening. It is especially useful for researchers of Chinese folk opera.

In her dissertation, "A Study of the History of Chinese Opera Performance," Dr. Sheng Wen focuses on a systematic study of the history of Chinese opera performance. She discusses in detail the three stages of opera performance: the exploratory period, the formative period, and the mature period. She also concludes that the exploratory period from the beginning of the last century to the founding of the People's Republic of China was characterized by the transition from "folk singing" to "opera singing", and that its performance was characterized by a combination of "virtual and real, with the real being the main focus." "It is characterized by a combination of virtual and real, with reality as the main feature. After the founding of the PRC and before the Cultural Revolution, it was the process of nationalization of the American voice, and the performance style at this time was mainly to highlight the heroic role of the "type" characteristics. From the post-Cultural Revolution period to the present day of the 21st century, the performance art of Chinese opera has slowly recovered and gradually matured, from "American singing" and "national singing" to a great collision. After that, even the half-American and half-ethnic "folk-american singing" and "multiple singing" have emerged, and the comprehensive use of these singing methods has a crucial influence on Chinese opera performance.

Dr. Li Wei, in his dissertation, "An Examination of the Process of the Chineseization of American Singing in the Perspective of the History of Chinese Opera," systematically discusses the process of mutual collision and fusion between the Western school of American singing and the local Chinese folk school and folk opera schools. He argues that Chinese listeners prefer "Chinese" and "localized" styles, and the situation of "Chineseization of the American voice" has emerged, making Western and ethnic singing methods grow together and The two have mutually influenced and promoted each other, enriching the variety of vocal singing techniques in China. He also starts from the beginning of the Chineseization of the American voice in the 1930s and 1940s, to the difficult period of the Chineseization of the American voice in the 1950s and 1960s, and then to the deepening of the Chineseization of the American voice in the 1980s and 1990s, objectively revealing the diversified evolution of Chinese opera in the new era and the contemporary and international nature of the Chineseization of the American voice, which has shown a promising prospect for the development of Chinese opera and singing standards.

In his article "A Study of the National Style of Chinese Opera Music in the 20th Century," Guo Ronglong provides an overview of the historical development of Chinese opera. Based on the development of Chinese folk opera compositions, he elaborates on two aspects, namely the inheritance of national culture and the performance of national singing. He also provides an in-depth analysis of the national style of Chinese opera music composition from the aspects of Chinese opera's borrowing and absorption of opera, the musical genre of folk songs and opera music image shaping, and the use of national tonal composition techniques in opera. After that, he also looks forward to the future of Chinese opera, and believes that it is most important to deal with the national and global aspects of Chinese opera.

In his paper "The Evolution of Chinese Folk Opera Singing Styles", Cheng Yu gives a concise overview of Chinese folk opera and its singing styles, and analyzes the singing styles of the most representative opera artists in different periods, while conducting a comparative study. He concludes that the style of singing was first based on the "earthy voice", and then it was borrowed from opera and absorbed the advantages of folk singing, Western singing and popular singing, and gradually matured. He also looks forward to the trend of diversification of Chinese folk opera singing styles after the twenty-first century, and puts forward some rationalization suggestions to address the many problems that exist in Chinese folk opera, which are of certain significance.

In her article "An Experiment on the National Character of Chinese Opera and the Advantages of Future Development," Lv Shuang outlines the development trajectory of Chinese opera, and also elaborates on the creative characteristics of Chinese opera at different stages of initial exploration, experimental development and mature harvest, and lists the representative works of each period. She argues that the national character of Chinese opera is the most important thing, and it is also a necessary quality to reflect the Chinese national music style. She also analyzed where the strengths of Chinese opera's future development lie: only by adhering to its own national identity can it enter the world's artistic treasures.

In her paper "The Stylistic Characteristics of Yin Qing's Folk Opera Composition", Zhou Xuefei introduces in detail the artistic career of composer Yin Qing and the characteristics of the subjects of his works, among which the main melodic themes and military themes are the important areas of his compositions. She selects the latest work of Yin Qing's epic opera *The Long March* as the object of her study, and analyzes the background, characteristics, and innovations of the opera, the diversity of musical forms and the combination of folk and

American singing being the most significant artistic features of the opera. She also selects two famous operas from the opera and analyzes their structure and vocal singing techniques, thus summarizing the typical stylistic characteristics of the opera's lyricism, ethnicity and modernity. These theories of hers are of reference value to the writing of this paper.

In his paper "A Study of the Musical Image of Revolutionary Heroes in the Opera <Long March>", Zhou Xianmin firstly outlines the background of the creation of the opera "Long March", and then briefly analyzes the source of the opera, which comes from the real historical materials of the Chinese Revolution. It is also discussed that the work is a masterpiece that combines ideology and artistry, and its core theme is to promote the "spirit of the Long March"; its artistic creation is also a blend of Chinese folk opera and Western opera, forging the artistic characteristics of Chinese style. In particular, the opera portrays a group of revolutionary heroes without creating individual heroes, which is extremely rare in opera creation.

In his article "Analysis of the Characteristic Features and Singing Techniques in the Opera <Long March>Songs <My Beloved Can You Hear>", Xu Ruobin explains the value and significance of the creation of the opera "Long March" and argues that the opera is extremely important for promoting the "spirit of Long March" in the new era and for the creation of operas with revolutionary themes. In his article, he explained the value and significance of the creation of the opera "The Long March", arguing that the opera is extremely important for promoting the "spirit of the Long March" in the new era and for the creation of operas on revolutionary themes. He also summarizes the image and character of "Political Commissar Peng" through the analysis of the plot development and musical characteristics, and analyzes the main singing parts in terms of singing techniques, from the tone control in the expression of emotions to the tone and bite of singing, and finally summarizes the author's singing practice, thus profoundly depicting the artistic image of the character. The author's artistic image and characteristics of the character are depicted. These ideas and summaries are of great reference value to the author.

Journals and magazines

In her article "National Love and Long March Soul - A Brief Analysis of the Artistic Features of China's Original Opera <Long March>" published in "The Voice of the Yellow River", Fan Mengni introduces the background of the creation of the opera "Long March" and summarizes the artistic features of the whole opera, she believes that the main artistic feature of the opera is its nationality, in accordance with She believes that the main artistic characteristic of the opera is its national character, according to the regions that the Red Army passed through along the way, the composer must base his music on local musical materials, so as to better fit the real situation back then. As for the concept of the opera, she quoted Yin Qing's words: "Xuanxu tune must be Chinese, so that the people can listen to it smoothly". She also summed up the diversity of techniques used by Yin Qing to make the Xuanxu tune both singable and very Chinese. The opera "The Long March" is both contemporary and innovative, breaking the single principle of using only one singing method in the previous operas, and fusing national, American and popular singing methods together to form a unique artistic characteristic.

Lv Shuyan believes that the opera "Long March" is a military opera with the theme of building a group of revolutionary heroes, which is different from previous revolutionary operas. "This opera is a standard "man's opera", full of masculinity, which is one of its most outstanding features. She believes that the opera "The Long March" has successfully portrayed many artistic images such as Political Commissar Peng, Captain Zeng and Saeko Hira, and has carefully analyzed and elaborated on both the dramatic and musical images respectively, presenting the inner spirit of these artistic images accurately.

In her article "Walking under the Light of Ideals - Listening to the Premiere of the Opera <Long March>" published in Opera, Zi Yin said that she personally listened to the live performances of the "Folk Voice Group" and the "American Voice Group" at the National Grand Theatre. She said that she personally listened to the live performances of the "Folk Voice Group" and the "American Voice Group" at the NCPA, and her evaluation of the performance of "The Long March" was very pertinent and to the point. She thought that Yin Qing's composing technique was very skillful, breaking through the rhythms of various phrases and lyrics, linking various difficult lyrics together with light and smooth melodies, and the music was both sentimental and lyrical, strictly adhering to the theme without any tricks; the author Zou Jingzhi's writing ability was also extraordinary, avoiding the real and complementing the imaginary, and using only a few simple characters, simple language and simple actions to explain many big historical events. She also believes that with Yan Weiwen as the main character, she is able to write a clear account. She also thought that the singers, represented by Yan Weiwen, were not bad in their interpretations, both into the drama and into the spirit, with their voices and emotions, and their performances were appropriate and loved by the audience. These descriptions by Zi Yin gave the author an immersive experience.

In his article "The Performance and Singing of Liu Pingquan in the Opera <Long March>" published in The Art of Singing, Huang Xunguo writes that he himself, as the actor who appears in the third act of the opera, plays the role of the character "Liu Pingquan" in the opera. He tells us from his own experience that Mr. Yin

Qing's opera "The Long March" was composed with the full integration of Chinese folk music elements. "The melody of Liu Pingquan is based on a Guizhou folk song and is sung in a folk style; the words are pronounced according to the local dialect. This includes a lot of tone, expressions and actions when singing, all of which must match the identity of the characters in the play, so that the characters can be played vividly and deeply. He also wrote out all the feelings of his live performance, which provided the most practical information for the author to analyze this part of "Liu Pingquan" in his thesis.

In his article "How I Composed the Opera <Long March>" published in China Art Daily, Yin Qing, as the composer of the opera "Long March", described in detail his excitement and worries when he just received the task of composing the opera, and also expressed the difficulties and confusion he encountered during the creation process, including choosing the style of music and the design of each singing section, as well as how to use the artistic image of the characters in the opera. He also expressed the difficulties and confusions he encountered during the creation process, including the selection of the music style and the design of each singing section, as well as how to portray the artistic image of the characters with what kind of music. It was only after he had made sufficient preparations that he began to compose. He chose to expand the dramatic conflict to highlight the dramatic effect of the music, he chose to use local musical material to reflect the national character of the opera composition, and he chose the romanticism of the revolution to replace the cruelty and hardship of war and marching proved to be successful. Yin Qing's own perception and commentary on the work as the composer is most enlightening to the author.

Lou Wenli published an article "A New Path for the Creation of Large-scale Revolutionary Historical Subjects Opera: A Review of the Artistic Features of Yin Qing's Opera <Long March>" in Chinese Literature and Art Review, in which he believed that the dramatic structure of the opera "Long March" is very well-proportioned, with a relaxed tension, and can complete the portrayal of the group of revolutionary heroes through the portrayal of typical characters. The artistic plot of the opera and the historical plot of the opera The artistic plot of the opera coincides with the historical events, and the realistic and realistic aspects of the opera complement each other. In terms of music composition, it fully embodies the creative thinking of "using music to structure the drama", in which the three vocal themes echoing the first and last are the backbone and core of the entire opera structure, and form a cross-cutting structural force. He believes that the "Chinese style" of the "Xuanxu" brings the audience closer to the opera, making it easier to understand and accept. The lyrical and beautiful arias abound in the opera, making it intoxicating.

In his article "Talking about the nationalization of opera art from <Long March>" published in Guangming Daily, Gao Yin talked about a series of thoughts that he triggered after watching the opera "Long March". He believes that one of the main issues is the nationalization of Chinese opera art. The composer has a great responsibility: in what form and with what emotion should he express the spirit and symbols of the Chinese nation? This is an extremely difficult question to answer. But Yin Qing was well prepared, and after appreciating thousands of songs of the Chinese Red Army, he did it. In addition to creating music in the style of the marching route, he also combined both national and American singing styles, which is an innovation in opera composition.

In her article "Opera <Long March>: Recreating a Period of Suffering and Splendor from an Artistic Perspective" published in Literary Arts Daily, Ren Jingjing commented that the opera "Long March" presents a major historical event with revolutionary romanticism and truly recreates the majestic historical picture of the Long March and the years of suffering. She also believes that The Long March is interlinked and lifelike, and forms a perfect combination in terms of plot creation, music writing and characterization. She also concludes that promoting the spirit of the Long March and propagating positive energy is the goal of this opera's creation and its artistic purpose. These accurate expositions and summaries have expanded the author's ideas for her thesis writing.

New Researches on Chinese Opera

The research in this dissertation focuses on six aspects of collecting literature on the selected topic: first, animated teaching agents; second, animated teaching agents teaching roles, third, animated teaching agents grid research, fourth, AR book research, fifth, animated teaching agents application research in AR books, and sixth, animated teaching agents and eye-tracking technology.

Compared with the auxiliary graphics such as arrows, colors and flashing cursors that appeared in the network environment in the early days, animated teaching agents have stronger interactivity, credibility and vividness, which provide great hope for broadening the way of communication between instructors and students, improving the attractiveness of the learning environment and motivating students to learn. For the promotion effect of teaching agents on learning effectiveness, there are mainly from the personality and teaching role of animated teaching agents image characteristics, learning material difficulty characteristics, and learner characteristics. There are also self-reports, questionnaires, and pre- and post-performance tests in the empirical methods used to study animated teaching agents. Here, we focus on the effects of animated teaching agents on learning outcomes, teaching role image and personality, and empirical methods to sort out the current state of research.

Conclusion

The significant learning gains in teaching agent settings appear to be due to the social nature of teaching agent interactions and are empirically supported (Graesser, Moreno, & Marineau, 2003; Moreno et al., 2000). Some have examined the existence and purpose of social agents, and some have examined the benefits of natural language, which once had a dynamic, interactive presence.

Graesser, Moreno and Marineau (2003) found empirical support for the use of natural language and assessment as a way for students to model their knowledge and respond in a pedagogically appropriate manner. In this experiment, students participated in computer literacy tutoring through interactions with AutoTutor (Graesser et al., 1999). Conditions testing the effects of the dialog included tutoring interactions with either relevant (i.e., tested in the posttest) or irrelevant (i.e., not tested in the posttest) content areas. The results of the study indicated that participants who conversed with AutoTutor in the relevant domain condition showed higher learning gains than those in the irrelevant domain condition. The researchers concluded that AutoTutor's conversation-mediated behavior had a positive impact on learning.

Moreno et al. (2000) were interested in examining the benefits of programming for agents from the perspective of motivation and interest. Their hypothesis is that the inclusion of educational agents promotes learning gains through the phenomenon of social agency alone. Participants interacted with constructivist instructional programs through computers under different conditions. The conditions included an intelligent body environment versus a non-intelligent body environment, an animated intelligent body versus a human face, and auditory versus visual instructions. The learning outcomes of this study showed significant differences in measures of transfer when learners were present in the learning environment. The researchers failed to find image effects when testing animated agents and videotaped humans. They also found that auditory instruction resulted in significantly higher memory compared to visual instruction. The study also showed that participants performed better in retaining, transferring and evaluating lessons when agents were taught in a personalized conversational style. These experiments support the phenomenon of learning through lively instructional tools in social settings. In the first two experiments, the authors concluded that their results support the use of instructional devices as a method to promote memory and transfer. More positive affective measures also suggest increased interest and motivation to learn under instructional conditions. The literature on educational agentic environments appears to be guided by advances in technology to create and implement them. Although empirical results are lacking to support the idea that agents themselves promote learning, the social aspects of instructional agent environments suggest that, when carefully designed, agents can serve as effective mentors or collaborators for students. Designers are working on student-centered learning environments that utilize a constructivist educational paradigm. With further advances in technology, it has become easier to create a dynamic, emotional conversation partner that can act as a mentor to students. These intelligent body environments offer a wide scope for further research, simply because of the rapid development of emerging technologies that allow for natural language processing and characters with human-like language and nonverbal communication.

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